

Import Necessary Libraries

```
In [ ]: !pip install scipy
!pip install pinguin
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
import seaborn as sns
import math
%matplotlib inline
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In [ ]:
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In [ ]: #Load data
df = pd.read_excel('FileName.xlsx')
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Test for Difference (Group Productivity/Precision)

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In [ ]: import scipy.stats as stats

#values for a and b are integers
stats.ttest_ind(a= groupa, b=groupb, equal_var=True)
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Equivalence test (Precision)

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In [ ]: from pinguin.equivalence import (tost)
x= interaction['Precision'] #column with precision values for interaction
y= element['Precision'] #column with precision values for element

#bound (float)-Magnitude of region of similarity.
#Note that bound should be expressed in the same unit as x and y

#paired (boolean)-specify whether the two observations are related or independent.

pg.tost(x,y, bound=***,paired=True or False)
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Subplots for Mean Threats in Each Group

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In [ ]: df.groupby('Threat category')['TP','FP'].plot(kind='bar', ylim=(0, 5),
                                                    figsize=(1.75, 1.75),
                                                    color=("black", "grey"),
                                                    legend=True)
```

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In [ ]:
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Threat category precision boxplot

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In [ ]: S=[] #input precision values for all each team in each category
T=[]
R=[]
I=[]
D=[]
E=[]
Group_Prec=[]

box_plot_data=[Group_Prec,S,T,R,I,D,E]
plt.boxplot(box_plot_data,patch_artist=False,
            showmeans=True,labels=['Group_Prec','S','T','R','I','D','E'])
plt.axvline(x = 1.5, color = 'black',
            linestyle = 'dotted',label = 'axvline - full height')
plt.title('Precision per Threat Category')
plt.savefig('name.png', bbox_inches='tight', dpi=150)
plt.show()
```

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